

REPORT ON THE AWARENESS RAISING CAMPAIGN ON NUTRITIONAL RECOMMENDATIONS

D6.6

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Short Description	
<p>This deliverable summarises the work and activities carried out throughout the FoodLAND project to raise public awareness about healthy and balanced diets and to disseminate and implement the nutritional recommendations developed by the FoodLAND Nutrition Working Group for the six countries in which the project has worked. Life events were combined with online activities to disseminate the dietary recommendations with the overall aim of raising public awareness.</p>	
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Introduction

Decades of shifts in food systems have led to a concerning rise in specific forms of malnutrition, juxtaposing issues like stunting and wasting with escalating rates of obesity and overweight. In African nations, these challenges manifest uniquely across different regions. These trends underscore an urgent need to align food supply chains with nutrition goals, particularly in ensuring accessibility and affordability of nutritious foods, especially for vulnerable demographics like children and mothers.

Over the past four years, the FoodLAND project has worked diligently to address the pressing issue of malnutrition in six African countries in Northern and Eastern regions, namely Morocco, Tunisia, Ethiopia, Kenya, Uganda, and Tanzania. The project's efforts culminate in a comprehensive set of 360 nutritional recommendations that are relevant, suitable and feasible to implement pursuing to combat the diverse forms of malnutrition prevalent in each of these areas, ultimately striving to contribute to the fulfilment of the Sustainable Development Goals, particularly target 2.2, which calls for the significant reduction of all forms of malnutrition.

The nutritional recommendations put forward by FoodLAND aim to bridge the gap between existing food behaviours and optimal nutrition. The nutrition working group worked with three key data sources for the development of the recommendations: an extensive desk review carried out for all the African countries involved in the project, surveys conducted in both urban and rural settings, with a specific focus on women with children in their first 1,000 days, and inputs from significant nutrition stakeholders, involved in the validation of the recommendations generated, identification of gaps in those recommendations, and generation of recommendation to close the identified gaps. D2.6 Report on Nutritional Recommendations submitted in M36 offers a comprehensive description and analysis of the work carried out to put forward the recommendations, including the nutritional gaps identified in each country.

Alongside the development of nutritional recommendations, FoodLAND partners have introduced 26 innovative food products and ingredients, including various nutrient-rich cereals, legumes, and vegetables. These have been transformed into nutrient-dense flours, protein- and micronutrient-rich snacks, and other food forms designed to enhance dietary quality. Many of these products offer healthier alternatives to low-nutrition snacks currently available on the market, while others have been processed or dried to improve shelf life while maintaining palatability. Aligned with the project's nutritional recommendations, these new products aim to support consumers in making healthier food choices, ultimately contributing to improved dietary habits and overall well-being.

FoodLAND has actively worked to ensure that its nutritional recommendations reach both the general public and key stakeholders, maximizing their impact and promoting healthy and diverse diets in the society. Through a combination of life events, educational materials, and strategic partnerships, the project has sought to engage citizens directly while also involving influential actors who can help amplify the message. By targeting multiple levels of society, from individuals to policymakers, FoodLAND aimed to create a ripple effect, fostering lasting change in food choices and nutritional awareness.

Reaching key stakeholders is crucial in the successful dissemination of nutritional recommendations, as their influence can significantly amplify the campaign's impact. While the recommendations are designed for the general public, engaging stakeholders such as health authorities, policymakers, healthcare professionals, and community leaders ensures wider dissemination through trusted and authoritative channels. These stakeholders play a vital role in integrating the recommendations into public health initiatives, educational programs, and community outreach efforts, making them more

accessible and credible to citizens. By leveraging their networks and expertise, the campaign can extend its reach beyond direct communication with individuals, fostering a broader and more sustained adoption of healthier dietary practices across diverse populations.

The approach to have the biggest impact, as well as activities have been outlined based on the collaboration between ELH, the project's Communication and Dissemination team, and the partners involved in the implementation of the dissemination activities in the African countries, namely the local coordinators at country level and the Food Hub facilitators. ELH provided African partners with a preliminary set of tools which they could use directly or adapt according to each country's needs and recommendations. This set of tools was in line with the agreements reached during the bilateral meetings between ELH and the African partners, which were arranged to ensure that the tools respond to the real needs and specificities of the regions where the nutritional recommendations need to be disseminated and implemented. D6.4 Tools for Dissemination of Validated Innovations and Dietary Recommendations collects and describes this preliminary set of tools.

The present deliverable provides a comprehensive overview of the materials produced, distributed, and utilized by project partners (adapted from the ones provided in D6.4) to effectively disseminate nutritional recommendations, together with the broad set of events and activities carried out by them to this end. It also details the various communication channels—both pre-existing and newly established—through which outreach and engagement have been fostered. By leveraging these channels, the project has worked to ensure that the nutritional recommendations reach the widest possible audience, fostering greater awareness and understanding. Furthermore, this report presents an impact assessment, incorporating both qualitative insights and, where available, quantitative data. Through this, the FoodLAND project aims to highlight the significant efforts made by all partners and the tangible outcomes achieved in promoting improved nutritional practices across diverse communities.

Laying the groundwork to raise awareness on healthy food habits: Surveys with urban and rural consumers

Although not directly part of the awareness-raising campaign on nutritional recommendations, the surveys conducted by FoodLAND partners in six African countries likely contributed to increasing awareness of healthy eating. Designed to expand knowledge of African consumers' food preferences, behaviours, and socioeconomic drivers while assessing dietary diversity, these surveys examined food provisioning and consumption habits in both rural areas—where Food Hubs were established—and their paired urban areas.

With over 7,000 citizens interviewed about their shopping and eating habits, the survey process itself may have influenced participants' awareness and attitudes toward nutrition. Reflecting on their dietary choices likely encouraged them to become more conscious of their eating patterns and potential areas for improvement. This self-examination fosters greater sensitivity to nutritional information, as individuals recognize the various factors shaping their food decisions, such as convenience, cost, and cultural preferences. Additionally, engaging in the survey process can spark curiosity and openness to new knowledge, making participants more receptive to nutritional recommendations for a healthy and balanced diet.

By actively considering their habits and comparing them to recommended guidelines, survey respondents may have gained a better understanding of the benefits of healthier food choices, increasing their motivation to adopt positive dietary changes. As a result, it is reasonable to assume that they became more sensitive and receptive to the nutritional recommendations promoted by FoodLAND in the final stage of the project.

Public events for/with citizens and stakeholders where the nutritional recommendations and the novel food products were disseminated

The FoodLAND African partners have demonstrated a strong commitment to disseminating nutritional recommendations, not only through the production and distribution of promotional materials but also by organizing local workshops and meetings. These events brought together key stakeholders—including health authorities, policymakers, farmers, and consumers—to share and discuss the recommendations, fostering greater awareness and engagement. By facilitating direct interaction and dialogue, these in-person gatherings played a crucial role in ensuring that the nutritional guidelines were effectively communicated and embraced by local communities. Below is a list of the in-person events organized so far across the partner countries:

[Nutrition Wellness Clinic Day in Uganda](#)

On 13 September 2024, the Makerere University organised the Nutrition Wellness Clinic Day, where they offered free services including nutrition guidance and counselling, and blood pressure and glucose screening. Sickle cell screening was also conducted to create more awareness in the community.

[FoodLAND disseminates its results in Kampala, Uganda](#)

On 29 August 2024, a FoodLAND Dissemination Workshop was organised by our Ugandan partners at the Makerere University in Kampala. Among others, they presented the developed novel food products, including sweet potato noodles, composite flours, and snacks/daddies. These products are highly acceptable hence they would open up new markets and contribute to higher dietary intake of protein and micronutrients such as zinc and iron.

[FoodLAND SUA team participates in Farmers' Day in Tanzania](#)

On 8 August 2024, the FoodLAND Africa team from SUA participated in the Farmers' Day, *Nane-Nane* for its name in Swahili. The FoodLAND team from SUA took part by showcasing the innovative technologies and some novel food product developed in the project, such as the fortified flour for normal and instant porridge. They received positive

feedback from the organizing team and from the farmers who visited the booth.

[Two-day conference for the dissemination of nutritional recommendations at Nyeri County, Kenya](#)

On 25-26 July 2024, the University of Nairobi partners held a successful two-day conference on the Dissemination of Nutritional Recommendations at Nyeri County.

The event was officially opened by the Nyeri County Director of Health and the Chairman of the County Assembly Health Committee gave a supportive speech. The event was attended by 40 politicians, 40 community health promoters and 80 household representatives.

[FoodLAND spreads solutions for farmers and nutritional recommendations in Nakaseke, Uganda](#)

On 16 July 2024, the FoodLAND partners at Makerere University organised a workshop in the Nakaseke district to present the progress made by the FoodLAND project in this district, including the nutritional recommendations. About 30 people attended the meeting., Some district officials contributed with their remarks, among others, Dr. Aliga Simon, Nakaseke District Health Officer.

[FoodLAND shows project findings and raises awareness of both technologies and nutritional recommendations based on research results in Kamuli, Uganda](#)

On 12 June 2024, the first dissemination workshop in Uganda took place, at the Kamuli Multi-Purpose Youth Hall. This meeting combined the participation of both stakeholders of the Kamuli district and FoodLAND researchers. Key District Officials remarked on different aspects of the health problems related to nutrition they cope with together with difficulties farmers experience in their business, adding that “the FoodLAND project has its objectives in the right place”.

[FoodLAND innovative products at the Nairobi Innovation Week](#)

On 8-10 May 2024, the University of Nairobi Innovation Week (NIW) annual event was celebrated, where fraternity and other interested parties showcased their innovations. The University of Nairobi FoodLAND partners were privileged to be part of the conference exhibitors.

The FoodLAND project exhibited five products; tree tomato Juice, tree tomato powder, bio-based packaging, pamphlets and posters on quinoa enriched products.

[Fruitful FNSSA Sister Project Synergy Summit event](#)

On 10-11 January 2024, several FoodLAND partners participated in the FNSSA Sister Project Synergy Summit event, together with partners of the other sister projects InnoFoodAfrica and HealthyFoodAfrica held in Helsinki, Finland. This was a unique opportunity to share the steps forward taken by the different projects on the path towards the transformation of the agri-food system in Africa. Wambui

Kogi-Makau (University of Nairobi) reported the FoodLAND research done on the nutritional recommendations

[Women in Tanzania empowered by the FoodLAND project](#)

During September and October 2023, the FoodLAND partner Helvetas organised two training events for women empowering in the two regions where FoodLAND has established Food Hubs in Tanzania: Mvomero and Kilombero. It was also supported by researchers from the Sokoine University of Agriculture (SUA).

The training covered several topics, including food and nutrition. Over 300 people (189 male and 128 female), from different age groups attended the first event and 34 the second one.

[Workshop about nutritional recommendations in Tunisia](#)

On 28 July 2023, the FoodLAND project INAT team held a workshop at their facilities dealing with the nutritional recommendations to be developed as part of the project's ambitious objectives. Participants, included national and regional public institutions, scientific researchers (INAT, ISACM, INRAT, INNATA), international cooperation agencies (FAO, WFP, IFAD, AICS), the NGO CEFA (the other

Tunisian partner in the project), and representatives of civil society, such as Culinary strolls and Dairy Club.

[FoodLAND at the Kitui Agricultural Show and Trade Fair 2023](#)

The FoodLAND partner University of Nairobi team exhibited novel quinoa products on 27-28 July 2023, at the Kitui Agricultural Show and Trade Fair. Exhibitors as well as visitors to the show tested different combinations of quinoa at the Ministry of Health Stand where the FoodLAND team was exhibiting the products.

[Conferences in Kenya for stakeholders' engagement and validation of nutritional recommendations](#)

In July 2023, the FoodLAND partners of the University of Nairobi, Kenya, have recently organised two conferences for stakeholder's engagement conference on nutrition recommendations in Kitui and Nyeri counties. Each conference brought on board 40-50 representatives of households, community groups who represent households and individuals in various forums (community health promoters/volunteers (CHP/CHV), government ministries that are closely aligned to human nutrition interests (health, agriculture livestock & fisheries, trade & industry, social & gender and the office of the County government).

[FoodLAND disseminates its results in Kampala, Uganda](#)

On 29 August 2024, a FoodLAND Dissemination Workshop was organised by our Ugandan partners at the Makerere University in Kampala. The principal investigator of FoodLAND at the Makerere University, John Muyonga, offered a general overview of the work carried out by the FoodLAND partners in Uganda, including the surveys to consumers and producers, and the developed products, including sweet potato noodles, composite flours, and snacks/daddies. They also shared reflector jackets and brochures with nutritional recommendations.

DALF reported having disseminated the nutritional recommendations during the technical meetings and information sharing sessions they hold quarterly in Kenya

On 18 October 2024, a joint EU projects meeting was held in Kisumu, Kenya, by Healthy Food Systems project. FoodLAND participated together with Healthy Food Africa, Afri, Practice, Agrifoodlink, and Change Maker projects.

Promotional materials produced by partners for the dissemination of the nutritional recommendations

As part of their efforts to promote the nutritional recommendations developed for their respective countries, the African partners of the FoodLAND project produced a variety of promotional materials, including reports, brochures, posters, and reflector jackets. These materials were designed to effectively communicate key dietary guidelines and encourage healthier food choices among local populations. While some of these resources were inspired by the preliminary set of tools shared with them—outlined in Deliverable D6.4—others were tailor-made to address specific regional needs and cultural contexts. This approach ensured that the dissemination strategies were both relevant and impactful, maximizing their reach and effectiveness in raising awareness about healthy diets.

REPORTS

University of Nairobi partners prepared a set of bulletins with the recommendations developed for each of the three counties in Kenya in which they worked in FoodLAND. Click on each picture to access the document.

BROCHURES

Brochure prepared by Makerere University partners for promoting their nutritional recommendations in Uganda, focusing on adults and elderly. Click on the image to access the document.

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POSTERS

ENAM prepared and delivered a broad set of posters, in English, French, and Arabic, covering different nutritional recommendations in Morocco. Click on each image to access the poster:

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THE LOWDOWN ON FATS

Eating small amounts of healthy fat can lower your risk of heart disease

Choose Unsaturated Fat (Healthy Fat)

- Choose olive oil, sunflower oil, rapeseed, avocado, and nut oils.
- Use rapeseed, sunflower, or nut oils for cooking.
- Use rapeseed, sunflower, or nut oils for dressings.
- Choose nut butter for spreads.
- Choose nut butter for dips.
- Choose nut butter for spreads.

Limit saturated Fat

- Choose lean meats with no visible fat.
- Limit processed meats like salami, chorizo, and bacon.
- Choose low-fat dairy products.
- Choose low-fat spreads.
- Choose low-fat spreads.

Avoid trans Fat

- Read ingredient lists and avoid partially hydrogenated oils.
- Read labels for trans fats. They are listed as "trans" or "partially hydrogenated" on labels.
- Avoid fried fast-food items, margarine, and shortening.

شراء الأغذية المنتجة محلياً

يمكن من تعزيز التجارة في منطقتك ويساهم في صحة البيئة

BUY LOCALLY PRODUCED FOOD

Promote your local business and help protect the environment

مارسا الرياضة!

20 دقيقة يوميا

أعد أجسامنا لممارسة الرياضة والعناية بجسمك جسدياً وعقلياً

WORK OUT

20 MINUTES PER DAY

Emphasize the significance of engaging in sports and maintaining both physical and mental well-being.

CHOOSE HEALTHY DRINKS

- DRINK ENOUGH WATER THROUGHOUT DAY AND ACCORDING TO YOUR NEEDS.
- DRINK PLENTY OF MILK WITH MEALS.
- LIMIT JUICES TO ONE CUP PER DAY.
- FAVOR NATURAL BEVERAGES OVER PROCESSED PRODUCTS.
- AVOID ADDING SUGAR TO DRINKS AND OVERLY SWEET BEVERAGES.

إختر المشروبات الصحية

- اشرب كمية كافية من الماء على مدار اليوم وحسب احتياجاتك.
- اشرب كميات كافية من الحليب مع الوجبات.
- حد من تناول العصائر إلى كوب واحد يومياً.
- تجنب تناول المشروبات المليئة بالسكر مثل المشروبات المحلاة.
- تجنب المشروبات المحلاة التي تحتوي على السكر المضاف.
- تجنب المشروبات المحلاة التي تحتوي على السكر المضاف.

اشرب الماء

كل جهاز في جسمنا يعتمد على الماء!

يحتل الماء ما بين 60 إلى 85% من أجسامنا، وفي المتوسط، نحتوي على 70 لتر من الماء في أجسامنا، و 22% من وزننا.

كما أن هناك مشروبات أخرى تمد الجسم بالماء، لكن لا ينبغي شرب الكثير منها لأنها تحتوي على السكر والملح.

للمساعدة على الشعور بالراحة، اشرب 20 لتر من الماء يوميًا.

اشرب الماء بانتظام من 15 إلى 1500 مل.

DRINK WATER

EVERY SYSTEM IN OUR BODY DEPENDS ON WATER!

Water represents 60 to 85% of an adult's total weight. From head to toe, it represents 63% of our blood, 70 to 80% of our organs and 22% of our skeleton.

Other drinks also provide water to the body, but it is recommended not to drink more than one glass of fruit juice per day and to prefer healthy prepared drinks to industrial drinks including alcohol.

To reach the minimum quantity of water (1.5L) to drink per day:

- Subtract 20kg from your weight.
- Multiply the result by 0.075.
- Add 1.5L.

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INAT prepared some posters/infographics/cards regarding the nutritional recommendations in Tunisia. Click on each image to access the file:

Makerere University partners prepared and delivered some posters regarding the nutritional recommendations for Uganda:

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SUA partners prepared and delivered a poster in Swahili for Tanzania entitled Good nutrition for Good health.

REFLECTOR JACKETS

Makerere University partners produced and distributed reflector jackets with information on nutritional recommendations in Uganda

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Press impact obtained

The FoodLAND partners leading the dissemination of nutritional recommendations actively engaged with local, regional, and national journalists to expand the project’s visibility and influence. Through interviews and published articles, they successfully brought greater public attention to the importance of healthy diets, ensuring that key messages reached a wider audience. This media coverage played a vital role in amplifying the impact of the project, reinforcing the relevance of the nutritional recommendations, and encouraging their adoption across different communities..

<https://foodland-africa.eu/2023/07/04/foodland-is-among-the-flagship-projects-at-sua/>

December 2024. An article about FoodLAND and its results featured the [8th issue](#) (page 11) of the Urban Policy Platform, facilitated by UN-Habitat, where the nutritional recommendations are cited.

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July 2024. INAT was interviewed for a podcast episode of the Tunisian Kalam Radio about consumers' behaviour studied and the nutritional recommendations developed.

July 2024. [Report on the work of FoodLAND](#) in Uganda, including the nutritional recommendations by UBC –the public broadcaster network of Uganda.

June 2024. Interview to Prof Susan Nchimbi-Msolla in the Tanzanian National TV TBC1: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kqhJFYZKRVE>

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Impact through the FoodLAND’s own online channels

The promotion of the nutritional recommendations through FoodLAND’s own channels –mainly website and social media– offered direct control over messaging, audience engagement, and brand identity. Unlike relying solely on external media coverage, these channels ensured that the project’s vision, objectives, and key messages were communicated consistently and accurately. This direct communication has been aimed at fostering connection with stakeholders, allowing for tailored content, such as the recommendations developed for a certain country, to resonate with specific audiences, whether they are researchers, healthcare authorities, consumer associations or individual citizens. Regular updates and interactive content also helped maintain interest and enlarge engagement over time, keeping the project, and particularly the nutritional recommendations relevant and visible.

The communication activities aimed at promoting the project’s nutritional recommendations through its own channels began in early 2024 and continued until the project’s completion. Over time, the focus of the content evolved—initially highlighting the nutritional recommendations developed for each country and later showcasing the innovative food products designed to support healthier diets across African communities. This dynamic approach ensured that the messaging remained engaging, relevant, and aligned with the project’s progress.

VIDEOS

The publication of videos has been particularly impactful, as they feature statements from project partners detailing their work with consumers and the key findings of their research. A total of 12 videos have been produced, either directly or indirectly related to the dissemination of nutritional recommendations. These videos have been made widely accessible through the [project’s website](#), [YouTube channel](#), and various social media platforms, ensuring broad outreach and engagement.

Below are the links to all videos related to the dissemination of FoodLAND’s nutritional recommendations. While some focus specifically on these guidelines, others address equally important topics, such as food security at the consumer level—an essential factor influencing nutritional outcomes. Additionally, the collection includes a video highlighting the role of women in the food value chain, released in celebration of the International Day of Rural Women, and another showcasing key innovations developed within the project, such as nutrient-enriched bean varieties designed to improve dietary quality.

FoodLAND Consumer research results
74 views • 10 days ago

FoodLAND NRs for Tunisia
36 views • 5 months ago

International Day of Rural Women
123 views • 4 months ago

FoodLAND nutritional recommendations at the Kenya K24 TV
38 views • 6 months ago

FoodLAND NRs for Ethiopia
70 views • 7 months ago

FoodLAND NRs for Uganda
42 views • 7 months ago

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FoodLAND NRs for Tanzania :
90 views • 7 months ago

FoodLAND NRs for Kenya :
52 views • 8 months ago

FoodLAND Food Safety Day :
47 views • 8 months ago

FoodLAND Nutrition Working Group :
25 views • 9 months ago

FoodLAND in the last stage :
162 views • 11 months ago

FoodLAND New legume local varieties :
72 views • 1 year ago

WEBSITE

The project's website was designed to serve as the primary communication hub, providing a central repository for key dissemination materials and project updates. It has been a key platform for sharing information about FoodLAND's objectives, activities, and results, ensuring accessibility to a broad audience.

To support the dissemination of nutritional recommendations, a [dedicated section](#) created and regularly updated with relevant materials and resources. This section has played a crucial role in raising awareness and providing stakeholders with easy access to the latest insights and guidelines.

Beyond this dedicated section, the website has also featured numerous news articles highlighting events organized by African partners to promote nutritional recommendations (see the links above)

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in the corresponding section). A total of 12 news items were published, further amplifying the reach and visibility of these efforts.

Website performance metrics offer a partial indication of the impact of the nutritional recommendations and their role in awareness-raising. Analytics reveal that the nutritional recommendations section ranks as the fourth most visited page, with 519 visits, surpassing even the news section in traffic over the past year. Notably, users have spent the longest time on this section—an average of 1 minute and 50 seconds—compared to the site-wide average engagement time of 1 minute and 1 second. These figures suggest a strong level of interest and engagement, reinforcing the website’s role in effectively disseminating nutritional knowledge.

SOCIAL MEDIA

Leveraging social media has proven to be an effective strategy for raising public awareness about FoodLAND’s nutritional recommendations and engaging diverse audiences. These platforms facilitate real-time interaction, allowing the project to share key messages, insights, and solutions in an accessible and shareable format.

Throughout the project’s duration, three main social media channels—[LinkedIn](#), [X](#) and [Facebook](#)—were actively used to promote FoodLAND’s approach and results, alongside a dedicated [YouTube channel](#) serving as the project’s video repository. In total, 53 posts were shared on X, 43 on LinkedIn, and on Facebook, only devoted to disseminate the nutritional recommendations, as summarized in Table 1 below.

To maximize impact, a transmedia storytelling approach was adopted, tailoring content for different platforms and formats to effectively engage various audience segments. Each post was visually supported with photos, videos, infographics, or GIFs to enhance appeal and engagement. Hashtags such as **#foodproducts #results #foodafrica #nutrition #local #NR #fooddiversity** were strategically used to increase visibility and discoverability, ensuring the content reached beyond

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FoodLAND's immediate followers. On international observance days, relevant hashtags were further leveraged to expand audience reach.

FoodLAND executed three dedicated social media campaigns to highlight different aspects of its nutritional recommendations:

- FoodLAND Novel Food Products by Country: A series of six posts, each following a consistent design, showcased the novel food products developed in different partner countries.

- FoodLAND Nutritional Recommendations by Country: A collection of five short videos was published, summarizing the work carried out in each country and the corresponding nutritional recommendations, along with a general explanatory video on the Nutritional Working Group.

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- Promotional Materials: Both ELH and project partners developed various promotional materials to support the dissemination of nutritional recommendations, which were shared across social media platforms. Examples of these materials are provided below.:

The abovementioned campaigns were complemented by additional posts highlighting partners' participation in dissemination events and observance of international days such as the **International Day of Rural Women, World Food Day** and **Biodiversity Day**.

Consistent activity on social media significantly contributed to expanding FoodLAND's audience and increasing engagement. By the end of the project, the number of followers who have been exposed to information about the nutritional recommendations had grown to:

- ✓ **LinkedIn:** 978 followers
- ✓ **Facebook:** 757 followers
- ✓ **X (formerly Twitter):** 344 followers

On LinkedIn, by far the most successful social media channel in FoodLAND 13,529 impressions were accumulated regarding the posts about nutritional recommendations shared on this platform. This indicator measures how many people saw the content, giving an idea of the overall visibility and awareness generated by the campaign. The "Top 3" posts on this channels regarding the impressions reached are as follows:

- [Brochure for the dissemination of Ugandan nutritional recommendations:](#)
Impressions: 1,099 | Reactions: 31 | Reposts: 14
- [Video of NR for Tanzania.](#)
Impressions: 978 | Reactions: 19 | Reposts: 1 | Comments: 2
- [NR for Tunisia.](#)
Impressions: 784 | Reactions: 19 | Reposts: 3

On YouTube, the abovementioned videos containing information about the nutritional recommendations had the cumulative number of 818 views.

Table 1. Posts shared on social media related to nutritional recommendations

Date	Topic	Links for the posts on different social media platform		
25 Feb 2025	Post about the novel food products developed in Uganda	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
24 Feb 2025	Post about the novel food products developed in Tanzania	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook

18 Feb 2025	Post about the novel food products developed in Kenya	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
17 Feb 2025	Post about the novel food products developed in Ethiopia	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
14 Feb 2024	Post about the novel food products developed in Tunisia	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
13 Feb 2025	Post and video about the work carried out with consumers	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
12 Feb 2025	Post about the novel food products developed in Morocco	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
16 Oct 2024	Post with statements by FoodLAND participants on the World Food Day	Post on LinkedIn		Post on Facebook
15 Oct 2024	Post and video in the International Day of Rural women	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
8 Oct 2024	Post about the dissemination activity in Kamuli	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	
4 Oct 2024	Post about the Dissemination Workshop in Nakaseke	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
1 Oct 2024	Post about the Dissemination Workshop organised in Uganda	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
14 Sept 2024	Repost of a post by FoodLAND researchers about the importance of creating nutrition awareness among adults in Uganda	Repost on X	Repost on LinkedIn	
13 Sept 2024	Repost of a post by Muhunsa Makerere University about the successful Nutrition Wellness Clinic Day	Repost on X		
13 Sept 2024	Repost of a post by the Nutrition and Dietetics Students' society of Uganda about the Nutrition Wellness Clinic	Post on X		
10 Sept 2024	Promotion of the leaflet produced by MAK for the promotion of NRs	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	
7 Sept 2024	Promotion of NR.:Buy locally	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
4 Sept 2024	Promotion of the nutritional recommendations for Tunisia	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	
4 Sept 2024	Repost of a post by a participant in FoodLAND in Uganda	Post on LinkedIn		
1 Sept 2024	Repost of a post by FAO on the World Food Day	Repost on X		
1 Sept 2024	Repost of a post by a participant in FoodLAND to engage people in physical exercise	Repost on X		
1 Sept 2024	Promotion of NR.: Work out 20 minutes a day	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	
26 Aug 2024	Promotion of NR.: help your baby grow up healthy	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
23 Aug 2024	Promotion of the bulletin for Kisumu county in Kenya	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
20 Aug 2024	Promotion of the bulletin for Kitui county in Kenya	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	
14 Aug 2024	Promotion of the report about the work of FoodLAND in Uganda by the public broadcaster network of Uganda: UBC.	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
12 Aug 2024	Participation of SUA team in the Farmers' Day	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook

8 Aug 2024	Interview to the UoN partners on NRs by the K24 TV national TV station in Kenya	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
2 Aug 2024	Promotion of NR.: Eat 5 food products	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	
29 July 2024	Celebration of the conference in Kenya for the dissemination of the NRs	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
24 July 2024	Promotion of the video produced by UoN partners about NRs	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
22 July 2024	Promotion of the nutritional recommendations for Ethiopia	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	
22 July 2024	Repost of a post by a FoodLAND researcher about the dissemination event in Nakaseke	Repost on LinkedIn		
17 July 2024	Promotion of NR.: Limit fatty & sugary food	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
15 July 2024	Promotion of the NRs for Uganda	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
10 July 2024	Promotion of the NRs for Tanzania	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
5 July 2024	Promotion of the bulletin for Nyeri county in Kenya	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
1 July 2024	Promotion of the section about NRs on the FoodLAND website	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
25 June 2024	Promotion of the NRs for Morocco	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
21 June 2024	Promotion of the NRs for Tunisia	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
18 June 2024	Promotion of FoodLAND participation in the Nairobi Innovation Week	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
13 June 2024	Promotion of the NRs for Kenya	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
11 June 2024	Promotion of the NRs for Uganda	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
7 June 2024	Promotion of FoodLAND in the Food Safety Day	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
4 June 2024	Interview to Prof Susan Nchimbi-Msolla in the National TV in Tanzania	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	
31 May 2024	Promotion of the NRs for Tanzania	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
29 May 2024	Promotion of the NRs for Kenya	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
22 May 2024	Promotion of FoodLAND in the Biodiversity Day	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
2 May 2024	Promotion of the video about the Nutrition Working Group	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
16 Mar 2024	Repost of a post by SUA about the bean varieties	Repost on X		Post on Facebook by SUA
6 Mar 2024	Promotion of the video about the project's last stage, including the NRs	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	
1 Mar 2024	Post about the novel legume line to improve diets	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
22 Feb 2024	Post about the novel legume line to improve diets	Post on X	Post on LinkedIn	Post on Facebook
20 Feb 2024	Post about the novel legume line to improve diets	Post on X		Post on Facebook
16 Feb 2024	Initial post about the 360 NRs developed	Post on X		Post on Facebook
14 Feb 2024	Promotion of the participation in the International Conference on Nutrition and Growth	Post on X		Post on Facebook

Impact through partners' channels for the dissemination of the nutritional recommendations

The dissemination of the nutritional recommendations through the project's official channels is crucial, but equally important is the role played by the consortium partners in amplifying this message. By sharing the recommendations through their own institutional channels—such as universities, research centres, NGOs, and other organizations with large, diverse followings—the outreach has been significantly broadened. Many of these followers are not part of the project's direct audience, allowing for the dissemination to reach new and wider groups. For example, a [post on X](#) by SUA promoting the novel bean varieties accumulated 2.882 views, as this institution has almost 13,000 followers on this social media platform.

Some partners have also made considerable efforts to create dedicated channels specifically for the promotion and dissemination of the nutritional recommendations. Find below some of these dissemination activities, and the indicator showcasing the number of people following it or having viewed the post/event, when available.

ENAM set up several channels under the name of “FoodLAND Morocco” for this purpose. These channels have been densely populated with ad-hoc produced promotional materials, including posters and videos, where they promote the different nutritional recommendations, they have developed:

[FoodLAND Morocco](#) YouTube channel. Some insightful data on the performance of this channel:

- ✓ More than 1,000 followers
- ✓ 54 videos uploaded with recommendations in English, French, and Arabic

[FoodLAND Morocco](#) Instagram channel. Some insightful data on the performance of this channel:

- ✓ More than 900 followers
- ✓ 78 posts, including posters and videos published in English, French, and Arabic

FoodLAND has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 862802.

The views and opinions expressed in this document are the sole responsibility of the author and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.

[FoodLAND Morocco](#)
Facebook channel.

[FoodLAND Morocco](#)
X channel.

UoN also made an effort to establish and feed their own channels for the dissemination of the nutritional recommendations in Kenya:

Website: foodland.uonbi.ac.ke/

This website contains the bulletins UoN prepared for each of the counties participating in the project with the tailored nutritional recommendations.

[FoodLAND NRS](#) Tik Tok channel, where they published a video they produced to promote the nutritional recommendations developed for Kenya.

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Assessment of the amount of people reached by activities carried out for the dissemination of the nutritional recommendations

The FoodLAND project implemented a comprehensive awareness-raising campaign to promote nutritional recommendations across multiple platforms, including official project channels, social media, institutional networks, public events, and media engagement. A key aspect of this campaign was the promotion of novel food products, emphasizing their alignment with the nutritional recommendations to encourage healthier diets.

Given the campaign's geographical spread across six African countries, providing an exact quantitative assessment of its total reach is challenging. However, the diverse dissemination strategies ensured broad exposure, while engagement metrics and participation figures indicate strong public interest.

Public events played a crucial role in direct engagement with communities, with thirteen dissemination events organized to share the recommendations with key stakeholders, consumers, and farmers. Among these, the University of Nairobi reported reaching 1,750 participants, including men, women, youth, and agricultural value chain actors, while Ugandan partners organized five events that also drew significant attendance.

Partners' ambition to disseminate the nutritional recommendations as widely as possible can be also noticed on the effort they made to prepare their own materials and launch channels for their promotion. Regarding the promotional materials, ENAM's hard work must be emphasized. Not only have they produced wide range of videos and posters, but also make the most of them, posting them on dedicated online channels and displaying the materials physically, in locations with big transit, such as the ENAM facilities.

FoodLAND posters displayed on the walls and videos on the television at ENAM's facilities

The online channels different FoodLAND partners have set up for the dissemination of the nutritional recommendations have widely helped reach people otherwise would not have been aware of the project or its nutritional recommendations, if we look at the number of followers they attracted.

This is also applicable to the wider audience that has been reached thanks to the posts FoodLAND partners have spread throughout their institutional or personal accounts. These collaborators expanded the reach of the project's key messages, reinforcing its relevance and impact. A notable example includes SUA's post on X, which reached 2,882 views, benefiting from the institution's nearly 13,000 followers.

The mass media press impact FoodLAND has contributed to amplify dissemination of the nutritional recommendations. The total amount of press hits collected is not very high in quantitative terms, but it is from a qualitative point of view. In fact, Kenyan, Ugandan, and Tanzanian national TV stations

broadcast interviews with FoodLAND researchers, further extending the campaign's reach beyond digital platforms and people attending the events where the nutritional recommendations were disseminated.

FoodLAND's social media channels were another key pillar of the campaign, enabling real-time engagement and content sharing. In this regard, FoodLAND has made big efforts to engage people and offer insightful content. More than 50 posts have been published with content covering nutritional recommendations, almost all of which have been tailor-made posts, conceived and designed by ELH, the partner in charge of communication activities.

If we look to the number of followers, FoodLAND has collected been especially successful on LinkedIn, almost doubling the initial target number of followers established in the Communication Plan (D6.2). The reason for this might be the fact that platforms like LinkedIn focus on professional networking and knowledge sharing and therefore are more receptive to research-based content, data-driven insights, etc., which is the main type of content shared by LOWINFOOD. However, the impact reached on the other channels is also worthy of consideration. By the end of the project, FoodLAND's social media channels had amassed a total of 2,080 followers (LinkedIn: 979, Facebook: 757, X: 344), ensuring a sustained audience for the last stage of the campaign.

Last, but not least, the website has been another key contributor to public awareness-raising on nutritional recommendations. Although the total number of visits is not impressive, it has helped in the dissemination, as it served as a point of reference for those wishing to have detailed information about the nutritional recommendations in each country.

In conclusion, considering the cumulative reach of social media engagement, participants to dissemination events, media coverage, as well as partners' successful initiatives to amplify dissemination, it can be confidently stated that FoodLAND has achieved the initial goal of widely exposing African citizens to the nutritional recommendations developed. The Grant Agreement established a final amount of 5,000 consumers or citizens reached in each of the 14 cities.

In most cases, we can consider these amounts have been successfully achieved and even exceeded in some cases thanks to the combination of digital presence, public outreach, and stakeholder engagement. However, the considerable delays accumulated in the project progress, due in part to the COVID-19 pandemic, have affected the final development and delivery of results, also influencing the dissemination activities. Ethiopian partners have been particularly facing struggle, as the war in Tigray forced partners to postpone all their activities, and only when the conflict was over were they able to carry out them, being the nutritional recommendations one of the last results they were able to develop.

Dissemination of the nutritional recommendations: work in progress

All FoodLAND partners are aware of the importance of widely disseminating the nutritional recommendations they have produced and are strongly encouraged to continue in this dissemination even after the project is ended. They have planned organising community awareness events, in the form of village meetings, village health and nutrition days, participating in radio talks, developing other promotional materials, open days at the food hubs, participating in exhibitions.

